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The Effect of Using Youtube to Increase the Level of Listening Skills Among Non-Native Students of Arabic Speakers in Malaysian Universities

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Abstract

Learning through YouTube has become one of the main sources of learning in the student's life at the present time which provides illustrative images, scalability of knowledge, and ease of searching for sources of knowledge. It also provides the student with large areas of self-learning and the provision of knowledge according to the desire of the student. On the contrary, other learning sources, where knowledge and goals are limited as well as time and place. Therefore, the current study deals with knowledge of the students' performance in listening skills by using YouTube among students of non-native Arab speakers by adopting Connectivism Theory. To achieve the objective of this study, the researcher intends to use the questionnaire survey to measure the effect of using youtube to increase the level of listening skills among non-native students of Arabic speakers. The study sample size was 144 students selected through the stratified sampling method from non-Arabic speaking students at the International Islamic Universiti Sultan Abdul Halim Mu'adzam Shah (UniSHAMS). The study used (SPSS,25) to investigate the hypotheses. Furthermore, the study showed that using YouTube has a highly significant impact on increasing listening skills for non-native students of Arabic speakers.

Keywords: Youtube, Listening Skills, Non-Native Speakers, Arabic Languages

1.1 Introductory

In recent years, modern technology has provided tools that have played a major role in the development of teaching and learning methods. These methods have also provided an opportunity to improve teaching methods that will provide an effective educational climate that helps to stimulate students' interest and motivate them and face individual differences in an effective manner the technological revolution has produced many technological means such as the computer, which has been currently replaced by a smartphone (Barker & Sparrow, 2016). Meanwhile, linguists were not immune from the current developments in the field of modern technologies, due to their profound impact on the daily life of human being, so they researched and experimented to identify the educational capabilities behind these modern technological means and how to tame them to serve the language lesson and increase its performance (Aboashmah, 2015 & El Omari, 2014).

Meanwhile, the advancement of information and communication technology has influenced many things in human life, as for this rapid progress, the learning environment and education in our time today has evolved step by step to help us achieve the desired goals as well as in learning languages as a second language has developed educational programs (Ismail & Sahrir, 2017). According to Zinedine (2014), online educational programs for language teaching have evolved from e-books to advanced programs such as Facebook, YouTube, and Moodle, besides that students and teachers use smartphones to learn the language in the light of mobile learning. Technology has become an urgent necessity for students and teachers, which helps in accessing information at record speed and improve academic performance. It also assists the learner in educational activities without restrictions by having to be in a specific place as well as students and teachers have also become more use of technology content and more aware of its importance over time (Kulkuska, 2005; Alyobeay, 2017).

Technology has become an urgent necessity for students and teachers, whether it helps to access information at record speed and improve academic performance, also assists the learner in educational activities without restrictions by having to be in a specific place. as well as students and teachers have also become more use of technology and content and more aware of its importance over time (Kulkuska, 2005 & Alyobeay, 2017). Linguists were not immune from the current developments in the field of modern technologies, due to their profound impact on the daily life of human being, so they researched and experimented to identify the educational capabilities behind these modern technological means and how to tame them to serve the language lesson and increase its performance (Aboashmah, 2015 & El Omari, 2014).

In the middle east, for the past few years have witnessed a growing interest in the field of teaching Arabic and learning it for non-Arabic speakers, this interest has been demonstrated by holding international scientific conferences in more than one Arab country, including Morocco, Jordan and the United Arab Emirates. Arabic language for non-native speakers in particular, such as educational curricula and teaching methods, the preparation of Arabic language teachers, the use of modern technology and theories in teaching Arabic, and teaching Arabic for special purposes, As it concerned with educational institutions in this country to teach the Arabic language to non-native speakers, as was the students are also directed to obtain research master and doctoral degrees in this field.

Sherer and Shea (2011) point out that many universities have established channels on YouTube to display videos of their lectures through it and that the YouTube site is available for students and teachers to use effectively within the classroom and outside to help students in their learning and achieve learning goals (Wilkins & Watkins, 2011). According to Aoutaih (2009) and Escobar, Muñoz, and Silva (2019), E-learning plays a pivotal role in developing some language skills such as listening. The Arabic language, with its four arts of listening, speaking, reading and writing, is an integrated unit, However, the priority of listening and speaking skills is that they are the two basic skills that begin with teaching Arabic to non-native speakers (Aburezeqm, 2019).

Furthermore, listening skill is a way for the development of other language skills, The ability of the individual to listen automatically leads to verbal fluency, demonstrating the convergence of listening and other language skills (Morales, 2018). Moreover, Omar and Tenkari (2016) demonstrated that Some previous studies proved that the individual takes (70%) of his waking hours in a verbal activity distributed as follows (11%) writing, (15%) reading, (32%) speaking and (42%) listening. Likewise, the study of Bird (1953) showed that (42%) to listening, (25%) speaking, (15%) reading and (18%) writing. While Wilt (1950) explained that (57%) of the time spent in the skill of listening. The previous percentages associated with listening skills indicate how important this skill for communication in general and the field of teaching a foreign language in particular.

This study is motivated by the fact that the Arabic language in this era is attracting an increasing number of students who want to learn it, especially after it became the fifth Arabic machine in the world as the number of those who are constantly learning is increasing, which poses a challenge in how to teach it to non-native speakers, especially in teaching listening and speaking skills. Being one of the most important pillars on which the teaching of Arabic language to non-native speakers and the need to invest technology in the teaching process because it contributes to providing an interesting performance contributes significantly to the demand for

students to learn Arabic (The 2nd International Conference on Arabic Language Education, 2015 & the International Council for the Arabic Language, 2013).

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of using YouTube to increase the levels of Listening Skill among Non-Native Students Arabic Speakers in Malaysian Universities. E-learning has multiple tools, each with its usefulness to serve the educational process and helps students and teachers to obtain information and improve the level of performance in different ways and forms, There are Facebook, blogs, video sites and other sites that feature participatory content (Alkadam,2019). Study of Gentry(2008) illustrated that YouTube is one of the most important tools, which is considered the most famous and widespread in the world and researchers in the field of education and education work must study and take a benefit of the enormous advantages provided in terms of how much information available and free publication of videos where the learner gets easily.

1.2 Statement of the Problem.

The majority of university students and lecturers have smartphones which becoming more prevalent in the world at present for both personal and educational lands, especially in the field of languages. Unfortunately, some of them do not use them for educational or special purposes in learning Arabic as a second language (Ducate & Lomicka, 2013; Ismail & Sahrir, 2017). According to Zinedine (2014), the poor performance of students in recalling the vocabulary of the Arabic language and the unwillingness to learn is one of the reasons for the failure of students in the Arabic language in some Malaysian universities. Consequently, learning Arabic cannot be based on traditional learning, such as writing notes and lectures, as most Arabic lecturers prefer. Also, Bahraudin (2017) and Abdullahi, Rouyan, and Noor (2018) pointed out that Lack of exposure to the Arabic language because the use of the Arabic language is limited to the classroom, while sometimes the lecturers resort to giving lectures in the mother tongue due to lack of time, which leads to the poor performance of students. Thus, it needed to use YouTube because of its great impact on language learners (Orú et al., 2016). Moreover, Omar and Tenkari (2016) stressed that listening is an essential skill which is the key to the rest of the skills (speech, reading, and writing) and requires education, training, and practice. Therefore, the study suggested the need to giving attention to listening skills as a second language and train learners to use effective strategies that lead to language proficiency in listening skills.

In light of that, there is a need to improve the learning process in the Arabic language for non-native speakers, taking into account the conditions of modern technological progress in the development of educational methods. From this standpoint, the current research will try to find aids to overcome the problem of listening among students and one of these means is YouTube, which provides a huge amount of educational videos for learning the Arabic language such as (ArabicPod101.com, LearnArabicwithMaha, and Easy Arabic) Where learning Arabic through YouTube is one of the best options that can be used to learn the language from its speakers directly, which accelerates the learning process and makes it more acceptable to the learner.

Even though the studies were conducted in different countries, their conclusion quite similar to Abdulhameed and Alkhawaldah (2018) who conducted a study on the impact of an instructional program based on using social networking sites on improving Arabic writing Skill. The studies agreed to confirm the listening skill as a fundamental requirement and a major objective in learning second languages as well as the effectiveness and impact of using a computer and mobile-assisted in acquiring language learning skills in learning languages for non-native speakers. Furthermore, based on the results of previous studies that indicated the importance of educational videos because of its impact on increasing the progress of students in various subjects, whether school or university. The study noted that the use of YouTube sites as a source of videos is relatively few, especially in Malaysia. The purpose of the research was to define the effectiveness of the participatory learning program on Facebook in improving writing skills. The study posited that the necessity to activate participatory learning through social networking in teaching and writing skills. Abdulhameed and Alkhawaldah (2018) found that there were statistically significant differences in promote of the experimental group, this means E-learning encourages students to learn which leads to a significant increase in the performance of students in experimental

groups. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the effectiveness of using YouTube to increase the levels of Listening Skill among Non-Native Students Arabic Speakers in Malaysian Universities.

1.3 Research Questions.

Arrived from the statement of the problems above, the study developed three research questions to achieve the objectives of the study. The following research questions are therefore considered relevant to the study:

- i. What is the opinion of utilizing YouTube by non- native Arabic speaking students among some Malaysian universities?
- ii. To what extent is the use of YouTube increasing the level of listening by Youtube?
- iii. What is the causality of using YouTube and increasing the level of listening skills?

1.4 Research Objective.

Based on the research question above, the study is to ascertain the effectiveness of using YouTube to increase the levels of Listening Skill among Non-Native Students Arabic Speakers in Malaysian Universities. However, the specific objectives are highlighted as follows:

- i. To determine the opinion of utilizing YouTube by non- native Arabic speaking students among some Malaysian universities.
- ii. To investigate the relationship between using YouTube and increasing the level of listening by Youtube.
- iii. To examine the causality of using YouTube and increasing the level of listening skills.

2.1 Review of Related Studies

Certainly in the field of learning through website and applications, studies have been conducted to give more insight on the impact of the use of modern technology such as Computer and a Mobile Assisted Language Learning in the acquisition of language skills some of them deal with technology in general and YouTube, in particular, to teach and learn the Arabic language for non-native speakers. According to Rice, Cullen, and Davis (2011) assert that utilized the internet in the field of education has a highly positive effect on learning and teaching. Therefore, the fact that the Arabic language for non-native speakers is in the form of learning foreign languages, it is necessary to refer to those studies.

Similarly, Al-Arabey (2014) conduct an empirical study on using blended learning to improve listening comprehension. The research objective was to examine the impact of using blended learning to improve listening comprehension. The study adopted an experimental research design and sample 10 from Arabic language learners. In the same vein, Abou roman and Hamdy (2018) researched on teaching listening for non-native speakers in Jourdan. Their study aimed to measure the effect of using Mobile Learning to obtain listening and speaking skills. Al-Arabey (2014) used to test for listening comprehension. Similarly, Abou roman and Hamdy (2018)) use tests for listening and speaking skills, and 25 respondents participated fully in the study and found Mobile Learning, as well as blended learning, has a positive significant impact to increase listening skills. Also, Alsaleem (2013) carries out an empirical study on the effect of WhatsApp toward obtaining the vocabulary. The study aimed to determine the effect of electronic dialogue in WhatsApp on improving the writing of English as a second language. Likewise, Ismail and Sahrir (2017) researched the effectiveness of WhatsApp to gain the vocabulary. During the experiment of the study in which, Alsaleem (2013) made use of 30 female Saudi students as respondents. Their data analyses were done using ANCOVA. Findings revealed that there is a difference between pre and post writing in for students who have conducted an electronic dialogue. Also, Ismail and Sahrir (2017) used a stratified sampling method in the study with a sample of 30 students. The study found that there were statistically significant differences in promote of the experimental group.

In the same context Ahmad, Sudweeks, and Armarego (2015) research on the effect of Mobile Assisted Language Learning to obtain English vocabulary in Australia. The study sample was 6 immigrant women via utilizing pre and post-interview. The study implied that there was a positive response of the respondents towards

the mobile learning experience in acquiring their vocabulary easily and comfortably which reflected on their confidence. Also, Atia (2014), conducted an empirical study on teaching Arabic as a second language. The research objective was to measure the attitudes of Arabic students as a second language towards using mobile and identifying their training needs. The study adopted a quantitative research design and a sample of 105 students from King Saud University in Saudi Arabia. The study using a questionnaire and found positive attitudes to using Mobil for learning. The study suggested taking advantage of the useful and educational benefits of this positive in the application of this model on students.

Even though the studies were conducted in different countries, their conclusion quite similarly to Abdulhameed and Alkhawaldah (2018) who conducts a study on the impact of an instructional program based on using social networking site on improving Arabic writing Skill, the purpose of the research was to define the effectiveness of the participatory learning program on Facebook in improving the writing skill. The study posited that the necessary to activate participatory learning through social networking in teaching writing skills. They found that statistically significant differences in promote of the experimental group mean E-learning helps and encourages students to learn which leads to a significant increase in the performance of students in experimental groups.

In the light of YouTube studies, researchers have tried to shed light on the vital role of YouTube videos for teaching and learning in educational improvement. Eick, Charles, David, and King (2012) discuss the YouTube influence on enhancing students learning At the university of the USA. Participants of their study consisted of 174 students and found that the videos helped to attract the attention of students to understand and remember the scientific material easily and students expressed their preference for high-quality short videos linked to the content accurately and directly. Savas (2012) conducted a similar study on the influence of youtube. Aimed to determine the effect of using YouTube on methods of teaching teachers of English as a second language in public universities in Turkey. The sample was 40 students and the result showed the usefulness of using videos in teaching as it contributed to improving students' skills in learning English.

In the context of listening skills, Rahimi and Soleymani (2015) sample 25 students whos studying English as a second language to experiment tow groups of students. the finding from their study revealed that the experiment group get the positive impact of using Mobile Learning in listening comprehension, and reduce anxiety and reduce fear, which enhanced their listening skill. The study suggested that to follow the research on the impact of mobile learning technology on the development of other skills.

A recent inference from Al Kidam (2019), examines the effect of YouTube on developing the level of listening speaking skills. The study comprises 42 students and applying the descriptive-analytical method by questionnaire. The research found the student's level of using YouTube was moderate, while, there was a significant impact to increase listening and speaking skills.

Also, Al lat (2018) sample was 77 students divide to tow group, YouTube group was 16, the Facebook group and 34 traditional group was 27, and analysis was done using an experimental method. The finding was there was a significant effect of using YouTube and Facebook on promoting the performance due to both of experimental group. Meanwhile, Ateiat (2018) considers a study on kindergarten to investigate the effect of YouTube on the teaching speaking skill. The study has a total number of 31 kids. Observation tools were used to measure speaking skills. Ateiat (2018) found YouTube has a great effect on increasing speaking skills. Both studies have similar research purposes with the same independent variable of YouTube in the studies. However, in addition to an understanding of this review on YouTube and increase level of skills and improve the performance of students, it can be concluded that there was an effect of using YouTube on increase level of skills as most authors cited in this review indicated a positive relationship between using YouTube on increase level of skills(Al Kidam,2019; Ateiat,2018& Al lat,2018).

The studies agreed to confirm the listening skill as a fundamental requirement and a major objective in learning second languages as well as the effectiveness and impact of using a computer and mobile-assisted in acquiring language learning skills in learning languages for non-native speakers. Furthermore, based on the results of previous studies that indicated the importance of educational videos because of its impact on increasing the

progress of students in various subjects, whether school or university we note that the use of YouTube sites as a source of videos is relatively few, especially in Malaysia. In light of this fact, the present study specified the following questions and objectives of the study.

2.2 Theoretical framework and Methodology

2.2.1 Constructivism learning theory

Constructivism theory refers to a set of educational processes that focus on the learner, which means that teaching is based on the interactive process taking into the students' tendencies and needs. Simultaneously, Constructivism theory focuses on building new knowledge in the light of past experiences of the learner by considering the environment in which teaching and learning have taken place (Johnson, 2004). Consequently, learning is not the transfer of knowledge by the teacher but is the construct of knowledge in which learners performed it during the interaction with the learning environment.

There are some of the models that exist in the education teaching and learning process based on constructivist learning theory. The current study will use the five E Model which developed by Roger Bybee (1990). According to Cahyarini, Rahayu, and Yahmin (2016), this model is one of the teaching models based on constructivist philosophy that emphasizes the active role and the critical thinking of the learner during an educational situation. The Model components consist of five phases which are represented in Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, and Evaluate, these phases will use for a teaching plan. The phases are shown in the graphic below:

Fig.1: Five E instructional model

Several studies were conducted to test the effectiveness of the constructive learning model to improve the level of students and confirmed that the significant and effective of 5 E instructional model to increasing academic achievement and developing positive attitudes towards learning in various fields, especially teaching foreign languages, such as Duran and Duran (2004); Gillies, Nichols, Burgh, and Haynes (2012); Skamp (2012); Dorji, Panjaburee, and Srisawasdi (2015) and Jogan (2019). The use of constructive learning model in teaching Arabic helps for getting information anytime and anywhere they want from more than one source and also allow students to express their idea in Arabic. Likewise, linking the educational material to the websites supported by audio and video will help non-Arabic-speaking students to listen more than once to the video which leads to confirm the information in their minds.

The purpose of teaching Arabic to foreigners is not only to know the grammar but to be functional and identical to the lives of students. This is consistent with the constructivist theory that teaching provides a great opportunity for students to communicate their knowledge with their daily experiences outside the classroom. Moreover, learning at the university level differs from educational levels before, the students at this level are required to be more effective than lecturers who teach them language skills. The impact of constructivism theory will be more useful particularly when the theory merges with technology, the learner will become more interesting and active related to what they learn. Furthermore, Constructive theory fits with learning to listen to non-native Arabic speaker students through YouTube, where the student is the one who builds his idea himself

with all activity and the teacher plays the role of encouragement and guidance to sources of information. Likewise, teachers will get an impact by changing their method on teaching style from the sender of knowledge to guiders in the learning process.

Through the Connectivism model, learning takes place in a democratic atmosphere that provides an opportunity for active interaction among students each other between students and science. this theory links knowledge and technology which makes learners in constant thinking that leads to the development of language skills of learners as well as provides an opportunity for learners to correct the misconceptions they may reach through the dialogue sessions held by traditional methods. Also, learners create knowledge in their attempt to understand experiences. According to Darrow (2009), the theory provides activation among all involved in the learning process. Thus, Connectivism Learning Theory considers as a significant theory for life long learning. Likewise, Davis, Edmunds, and Kelly-Bateman (2012) assertion that permit the future of education to be seen in an optimistic, this is because the majority of students co-create knowledge in a global society.

In this respect, the current study applied Connectivism Theory, because it links learning with YouTube and this is very important to give students the ability to listening to the educational material more than once. Also, the student will not be restricted by a certain time and place that can be re-annotated multiple times. Hence, the students develop a sense of belonging to the increased knowledge because the site provides clear voice and expressive images. Moreover, the Connectivism theory makes the learner the center of the educational process with the freedom to search and choose the audio material that fits their interests as well as allows the student to interact positively which in turn helps to increase performance.

3. Methodology

According to Martin and Guerin (2006), research methodology was grounded on the summary of the systematic investigation, procedure, sample selection, and analysis, which were conducted in the research. Meanwhile, the main purpose of this study is to examine the effect of using Youtube to increase the level of listening skill among non-native student of Arabic speakers in Malaysian Universities, a self-administered questionnaire was developed to collect respondent's data from the Malaysian students of International Islamic Universiti Sultan Abdul Halim Mu'adzam Shah (UniSHAMS). The survey questionnaire has consisted of four parts. Primary data was collected by distributing questionnaires. Especially, data was collected from the Faculty of Usool Edin (Islamic Foundations); Faculty of the Arabic language; and Faculty of Sharia and Law.

Respondents were asked to assess the items of different variables such as the opinion of students, increasing listening by Youtube, using Youtube, and listening skills based on 5-point Likert scales that range from strongly disagree (SD: 1) to strongly agree (SA: 5). Therefore, this study distributed 150 questionnaires to target respondents (Malaysian non-native Arabic students of Universiti) and via face to face students' survey at Malaysian Islamic Universiti using convenience sampling method, as it is the easiest to conduct with a large number of sample sizes as suggested by Hong, Thong, & Tam, (2004). Both descriptive and inferential analysis was employed to examine the effect of using Youtube to increase the level of listening skill, as it was a meaningful transforming statistical data into a linear combination of constructs (Hair et al., 2014). The survey research makes use of the fundamental information and Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS version 25) that carried out to examine the relationship among the constructs which influence using Youtube to increase the level of listening skill among non-native student of Arabic speakers in International Islamic Universiti Sultan Abdul Halim Mu'adzam Shah (UniSHAMS).

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation of Results

4.1 Response Rate of Distribution

In this research study, a total number of 150 questionnaires were distributed to the target respondents, of which 144 questionnaires were received. We found there are some errors or rest incorrectly and incompletely answered

a questionnaire by the respondent. After completed the screening process of the questionnaires, 140 questionnaires were found valid for data analysis, which represented a success rate of 93% that was considered satisfactory in view of time, certainty, cost, and geographical constraints. Table 1 indicates the summary of the response rate of the questionnaire survey distributed to the target respondents.

Table 1: Response Rate of Distribution

Descriptions	No of Respondents
Distributed Questionnaires	150
Retrieved Questionnaires	144
Usable for further Analysis Questionnaires	140
Unusable Questionnaires	4
Response Rates	93%

4.2 Reliability and Validity Analysis

Reliability coefficient measurement refers to the stability and consistency of the mechanism. Thus, this method shows reliability through examining the internal consistency of the research questionnaires, in which Cronbach's alpha of this study ranged from 0.727 to 0.869 which was considered a high-reliability coefficient of the data analysis. Jaapar, Endut, Bari, and Takim (2009) stated that Cronbach's alpha should be from 0.0 to 1.0, but 0.70 is deemed to be indicative of good scale reliability as suggested by Hair et al. (2016). Therefore, the reliability of this instrument was satisfactory. Based on the validity of the instrument of the variables, the exploratory factor analysis for the variable (Opinion of students; Increasing listening by Youtube; Using Youtube; Listening skills) is used by principal axis factoring extraction with varimax rotation. Exploratory factor analysis for variables, all items were found for analysis and the result showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling was adequate (Opinion of students 0.720; Increasing listening by Youtube 0.750; Using Youtube 0.678, and Listening skills 0.893). The total percentage of variance was explained in Table 2, in which 54.27% was explained for the total percentage of the variance of variables. The factor loading of each item was greater than 0.55. The factor loadings of items are greater than 0.50, indicates excellent. Pallant (2010) stated that a validity coefficient should be greater than 0.50. Hence, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) is considered as higher validity of all the variables. Table 2 shows a summary of the reliability and validity of the measurement of the variables used in this study.

Table 2: Reliability and Validity Analysis

Descriptions	Items	Cronbach Alpha	KMO
Opinion of students	7	.815	.720
Increasing Listening by Youtube	6	.727	.750
Using Youtube	5	.781	.678
Listening skills	9	.869	.893

4.3 Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Table 3 presents the respondents' perception of all the variables of a non-native student of Arabic speakers in Malaysian Universities. The examination of the results reveals the respondents' attributes of Opinion of students; Increasing listening by Youtube; Using Youtube; and listening skills in Malaysian Universities. The average score of mean and standard deviation is moderately good with a mean of 3.64 and the standard deviation is 0.882 which indicates that most of the non-native Arabic students incline to Youtube Opinion on listening skills at Malaysian Universities. Hence, the highest mean value is 3.95 for the construct of "product display is important" which followed by "Using Youtube" with mean 3.98. The lowest mean is 3.874 of the construct "Opinion of students" which followed by the "Listening skill" with the mean value 3.94. So, the respondents are more likely to state that the Malaysian Universiti of their preferred choice is Using Youtube because the standard deviation of using Youtube is less varied.

Also, testing for normality has been seen as an important and common procedure in statistical tests and multivariate data analysis in which many tests have been proposed. Therefore, it is important for researchers to examine the normality of their data distributions before proceeding to the analysis stage (Hair et al., 2014). The test for normality for this study was carried out using skewness and kurtosis. Hence, the skewness and kurtosis values of the variables are within the ± 2.58 acceptable range as suggested by Tabaniche and Fidel (2007). The entire constructs are said to be normal.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics and Normality Test

Constructs	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Opinion of students	3.874	.803	-1.07	.243
Increasing Listening by Youtube	3.920	.790	-1.32	1.27
Using Youtube	3.977	.848	-1.29	.88
Listening skills	3.940	.849	-1.42	.93

4.4 Correlation Analysis

As shown in Table 4 the correlations between the exogenous latent constructs were sufficiently below the suggested threshold values of 0.9. This shows that the opinion of students; Increasing listening by Youtube; using Youtube, and listening skills were not highly correlated. Pallant (2011) asserted that a correlation of 0 indicated no relationship at all, a correlation of 1.0 is an indication of positive correlation, and a value of -1 is a pointer of a perfect negative correlation. Cohen (1988) suggested the following guidelines as: $r = 0.10$ to 0.29 small; $r = 0.30$ to 0.49 medium; and $r = 0.5$ to 1.0 large.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix of the exogenous latent constructs

Construct	OS	ILY	UY	LS
Opinion of Student (OS)	1			
Increasing Listening by Youtube (ILY)	.514**	1		
Using Youtube (UY)	.428**	.573**	1	
Listening Skill (LS)	.540**	.643**	.628**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above signifies that the variables are significantly correlated to the fact that there is no variable with a value of 0.9 which indicated that there is no problem of multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2010).

4.5 Multiple Regressions and Hypotheses Test

Multiple regression analysis provides an avenue of neutrally evaluating the degree and character of the relationship between exogenous constructs and endogenous constructs (Sekaran & Bougie, 2012; Field, 2009). The regression coefficient employed to show the relative importance of each of the independent variables in the prediction of the dependent variable. Regression analysis was employed to test the hypothesis in this study; it is intended to investigate the relationship between predicting as well as the criterion variables respectively. For the conduct of regression analysis large sample is required and considered appropriate and also the underlying assumptions of multiple regressions were fulfilled as suggested by Hair et al. (2010).

4.5.1 Objective one – Opinion of Students and Listening Skills

Multiple regression analysis was conducted in determining the opinion of utilizing YouTube by non- native Arabic speaking students among some Malaysian universities. The model summary as indicated in Table 5 shows that R Square is 0.27; this implies that 27% of the variation in the dependent variable (opinion of students) was explained by the constant variables (listening skills)

Table 5: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	1.895	.278		6.815	.000
	Opinion of Student	.537	.070	.517	7.692	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Listening Skill

The dependent variable as shown in Table 5 explains the influence the opinion of utilizing YouTube by non-native Arabic speaking students among some Malaysian universities. This was used as a yardstick to examine the influence between the two variables (i.e. opinion of students and listening skills). According to the result in the table above the opinion of students, the t-test coefficient is 7.692 and the P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (i.e. $P < 0.05$). This means that these variables are statistically significant at 5% significant level. The overall summary of this regression outcome in relation to the coefficient of the opinion of students has a significant influence on listening skills. The finding is consonance with the finding of (Aksu-Ataç & Köprülü-Günay, 2018); (Sareepattanapol, 2017); (Worrawattananukul, 2016) & (Pimsamarn, 2011) who found that opinion of students has a significant influence on listening skills. Therefore, hypothesis H1 has supported.

4.5.2 Objective Two – Using YouTube and Increasing the Level of Listening

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to investigate the relationship between using YouTube and increasing the level of listening. The model summary as indicated in Table 6 shows that R Square is 0.34; this implies that 34% of the variation in the dependent variable (Using YouTube) was explained by the constant variables (Increasing the level of listening by YouTube).

Table 6: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	1.742	.247		7.063	.000
	Use Youtube	.548	.060	.584	9.159	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Increasing the Level of Listening

The dependent variable as shown in Table 6 explains to investigate the relationship between using YouTube and increasing the level of listening by YouTube. This was used as a yardstick to examine the influence between the two variables (i.e., using YouTube and increasing the level of listening skills). Based on the result in the table above using the YouTube t-test coefficient is 9.159 and the P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (i.e. $P < 0.05$). This means that these variables are statistically significant at 5% significant level. The overall summary of this regression outcome in relation to the coefficient of using YouTube has a significant influence on increasing the level of listening. Therefore, hypothesis H₂ is supported, the finding of the study concurs with Abou roman and Hamdy (2018); Al- Arabey (2014); Savas (2012) and Cullen and Davis (2011) they study disclosed that the usefulness of using videos in teaching as it contributed to improving students' skills in learning second languages.

4.5.3 Objective Three – Using YouTube and Listening Skills

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the causality of using YouTube and increasing the level of listening skills. The model summary as indicated in Table 7 shows that R Square is 0.40; this implies that 40% of the variation in the dependent variable (using YouTube) was explained by the constant variables (listening skills)

Table 7: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	1.397	.255		5.487	.000
	Use YouTube	.642	.062	.632	10.391	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Listening Skill

The dependent variable as shown in Table 7 explains to examine the causality of using YouTube and increasing the level of listening skills. This was used as a yardstick to examine the influence between the two variables (i.e. opinion of students and listening skills). According to the result in the Table, 7 opinion of students t-test coefficient is 10.391 and the P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (i.e. $P < 0.05$). This means that these variables are statistically significant at 5% significant level. The overall summary of this regression outcome concerning the coefficient of using YouTube has a significant influence on listening skills. Therefore, hypothesis H_3 is supported. Furthermore, the study conformed with Al Kidam (2019; Al lat (2018) and Rahimi and Soleymani (2015) their study found there was a positive relationship between using YouTube and increasing the level of listening skills.

6. Conclusion

In the light of the current result of the study and review of previous studies confirmed that YouTube is an effective medium and a useful educational tool, whether in research or educational presentations, and increasing educational skills as well, given its infinite digital content. Therefore, the study recommended that The necessity to use YouTube to acquire listening skills in Arabic language teaching centers, non-native students of Arabic speakers, due to the positive relationship this study showed in developing the listening skill. Likewise, encouraging lecturers in Arabic language teaching centers for non-native students of Arabic speakers to use YouTube in education in all skills, in addition to including educational video links for YouTube in educational syllabuses. Further studies in the future must examine the impact of using YouTube on increasing other skills, for instance, speaking, reading, and writing.

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